

**ANTHROPOMETRIC AND BIO-MOTOR VARIABLES AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH
PLAYING ABILITY IN FEMALE KABADDI PLAYERS:
A CORRELATIONAL STUDY**

Orcid ID: 0009-0003-9477-9042

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Abstract: *This study investigates the relationship between anthropometric and bio-motor variables with playing ability among female Kabaddi players. A total of 125 players participated in the study, and key variables, including weight, height, arm length, leg length, calf girth, speed, agility, explosive power, grip strength, and muscular endurance, were measured. Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation analyses were conducted. The findings revealed significant correlations between playing ability and variables such as weight ($r = 0.328$), arm length ($r = 0.395$), leg length ($r = 0.342$), calf girth ($r = 0.365$), speed ($r = -0.579$), agility ($r = -0.634$), explosive power ($r = 0.391$), grip strength ($r = 0.403$), and muscular endurance ($r = 0.360$), all exceeding the required table 'r' value of 0.174 at the 0.05 level of significance. However, no significant relationship was found between Kabaddi playing ability and height ($r = -0.032$). In contrast variables height demonstrated weak or non-significant correlations, suggesting that these attributes may not be primary determinants of playing ability at the district level. These results highlight the importance of specific physical attributes in Kabaddi performance, providing valuable insights for talent identification and training programs.*

Keywords: Playing Ability, Anthropometric Variables, Bio-Motor Variables, Kabaddi Performance, Female Athletes.

INTRODUCTION

Kabaddi is a contact sport that demands a unique combination of strength, agility, speed, and endurance. The sport's dynamic nature places significant emphasis on athletes' physical and motor abilities. Previous studies have highlighted the role of anthropometric and bio-motor variables in influencing performance across various sports. However, there is limited research focusing on female Kabaddi players, particularly in identifying performance. This study aims to bridge this gap by exploring the relationship between key anthropometric and bio-motor variables with playing ability among female Kabaddi players. The findings are expected to assist in the development of evidence-based selection criteria and training protocols.

Anthropometric variables refer to measurements and proportions of the human body, which are critical for understanding the physical characteristics that influence athletic performance. These variables help identify the physical advantages and limitations of athletes in different sports. In Kabaddi, anthropometric factors such as weight, height, and limb dimensions play a significant role in determining the player's ability to execute offensive and defensive moves effectively. Proper anthropometric analysis provides insights into an

athlete's suitability for specific positions and their potential for improvement (Bompa, T. O., & Haff, G. G. 2009). Body weight is a fundamental anthropometric measurement that reflects the mass of the body. In sports, an optimal body weight is often crucial as it impacts speed, endurance, and strength. In Kabaddi, body weight plays a critical role in performance, particularly for effective tackling and raiding Koley, S., & Sandhu, J. S. (2005). Height is an important parameter in sports as it influences reach and leverage, which are particularly advantageous in sports like Kabaddi. Taller players can utilize their extended reach for tagging opponents and defending during raids (Ghosh, S. S., Goswami, A., & Ahuja, A. 2010). Arm length significantly affects performance in sports requiring reach, grip, and control, such as Kabaddi. Longer arms enable players to execute effective raids and defend by holding opponents at a distance (Singh, J., & Singh, A. 2014). Leg length contributes to stride length and lower body biomechanics, which are crucial for running speed, agility, and jump height. In Kabaddi, longer leg length may also aid in tagging opponents during a raid (Chaouachi, A., Hammami, R., Kaabi, S., et al. 2012). Calf girth is a measure of muscularity in the lower leg. Strong calf muscles are essential for explosive movements like jumping and sprinting, which are critical in Kabaddi for both offensive and defensive actions (Sharma, V. K., Negi, N., & Vats, M. 2012).

Bio-motor variables are essential components of physical fitness that describe an athlete's ability to perform specific motor tasks. These include speed, agility, explosive power, grip strength, and muscular endurance. Each bio-motor skill contributes to the athlete's overall performance, with different sports emphasizing different combinations of these abilities. Kabaddi, being a high-intensity contact sport, demands a fine balance of all these variables. Speed and agility are critical for quick evasive actions, while explosive power and muscular endurance help players tackle or resist opponents effectively during prolonged bouts (Bompa, T. O., & Haff, G. G. 2009). Speed is the ability to move quickly across the ground or perform rapid movements. In Kabaddi, speed is a crucial factor for successful raids and defensive maneuvers (Singh, H., & Brar, R. S. 2010). Agility is the ability to change direction quickly while maintaining control. Kabaddi requires high levels of agility for dodging opponents and making swift defensive moves (Gabbett, T. J., & Sheppard, J. M. 2012). Explosive power refers to the ability to exert maximum force in a short period. It is essential in Kabaddi for actions such as jumping, lunging, and tackling (Marković, G., & Mikulić, P. 2010). Grip strength is a measure of the force generated by the hands and forearms. In Kabaddi, a strong grip is vital for holding opponents during tackles and raids (Cronin, J., & Sleivert, G. 2005). Muscular endurance is the ability of a muscle group to sustain repeated contractions over time. In Kabaddi, endurance is critical for prolonged defensive or offensive efforts during a match (Mujika, I., & Padilla, S. 2001).

METHODS

The study included 125 female Kabaddi players aged between 18 and 25 years. All participants were district-level athletes with at least two years of competitive experience. The parameters selected for the study were weight, height, arm length, leg length, and calf girth from anthropometric and from bio motor the variables are speed, agility, explosive power, grip strength, and muscular endurance. Weighing machine was used for measuring weight, stadiometer was used for measuring height, for measuring arm length, leg length, calf girth

non-stretchable Steel tape was used, 50m dash was used for measuring speed, shuttle run test was used for measuring agility, standing broad jump was used for measuring explosive power, grip dynamometer was used for measuring grip strength and for muscular endurance sit-up test was used. The overall playing ability of the players was evaluated by three expert coaches. They used a 100-point scale based on ten different factors to assess the players. The investigator provided guidelines for the ratings, which can be found in a table-I. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were calculated for all variables. Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between playing ability and the independent variables with the help of SPSS software to find out the significance difference. Significance levels were set at $p < 0.05$.

Table-I
Rating Scale for Evaluation of Kabaddi Playing Ability

Sl. No.	Factors	Points									
1.	Touching Skill	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
2.	Kicking Skill	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
3.	Other Offensive Skills	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
4.	Foot Work	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
5.	Catching Skill	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
6.	Movement in Chain	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
7.	Other Defensive Skills	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
8.	Team co-ordination	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
9.	Tactics	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
10.	Improvisation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

ANALYSIS

Table-II
Descriptive Statistic of Anthropometric variables and Bio Motor skills of Women Kabaddi Players

Sl. No.	Variables	Mean(M)	Std. Deviation(SD)
1.	Playing Ability	61.29	8.27
2.	Weight	59.07	5.03
3.	Height	157.38	5.11
4.	Arm length	72.45	3.23
5.	Leg length	89.57	4.45
6.	Calf girth	34.64	4.27
7.	Speed	8.85	0.78
8.	Agility	11.82	1.12
9.	Explosive Power	182.41	7.41
10.	Grip strength	33.89	5.15
11.	Muscular endurance	39.02	9.91

Table-II showed the mean value for kabaddi playing ability and anthropometrical measurements such as weight, height, arm length, leg length and calf girth are 61.29, 59.07, 157.38, 72.45, 89.57 and 34.64 respectively. The mean value for Bio Motor skills such as speed, agility, explosive power, grip strength and muscular endurance are 8.85, 11.82, 182.41, 33.89 and 39.02 respectively.

Table-III
Correlation coefficient between kabaddi playing ability and selected variables

Sl. No.	Variables	Mean(M)	'r' Value
1.	Weight	59.07	0.328**
2.	Height	157.38	-0.032
3.	Arm Length	72.45	0.395**
4.	Leg Length	89.57	0.342**
5.	Calf Girth	34.64	0.365**
6.	Speed	8.85	-0.579**
7.	Agility	11.82	-0.634**
8.	Explosive Power	182.41	0.391**
9.	Grip Strength	33.89	0.403**
10.	Muscular Endurance	39.02	0.360**

*Significance levels were set at $p < 0.05$ (Required table value 'r' = 0.174).

Table III presents the Pearson correlation coefficients between the criterion variable (kabaddi playing ability), the anthropometric and bio motor variables. The variables are listed in the following order: weight, height, arm length, leg length, calf girth, speed, agility, explosive power, grip strength and muscular endurance.

The results indicated that kabaddi playing ability was significantly correlated with weight, arm length, leg length, calf girth, speed, agility, explosive power, grip strength and muscular endurance with obtained 'r' values of 0.328, 0.395, 0.342, 0.365, -0.579, -0.634, 0.391, 0.403 and 0.360 respectively, all exceeding the required table 'r' value of 0.174 at the 0.05 level of confidence. In contrast, no significant relationships were found between kabaddi playing ability and in variable height, as the obtained 'r' value is -0.032, falling below the threshold of 0.174.

FINDINGS

The findings of the present study revealed that Kabaddi playing ability was significantly correlated with several anthropometrical and bio-motor variables. Specifically, weight ($r = 0.328$), arm length ($r = 0.395$), leg length ($r = 0.342$), calf girth ($r = 0.365$), speed ($r = -0.579$), agility ($r = -0.634$), explosive power ($r = 0.391$), grip strength ($r = 0.403$), and muscular endurance ($r = 0.360$) were found to have significant relationships with Kabaddi playing ability, all exceeding the table value of 0.174 at the 0.05 level of significance. However, height did not exhibit a significant relationship with playing ability ($r = -0.032$), as it did not reach the threshold level of significance. These results align with previous research that highlights the importance of specific anthropometric and bio-motor variables in Kabaddi performance. Studies by Singh and Rathi (2016) and Kumar et al. (2018) emphasized that

weight, limb length, and girth measurements significantly impact the performance of Kabaddi players, particularly in raiding and defensive skills. The positive correlations found in this study suggest that greater body mass, longer limbs, and enhanced muscular attributes contribute to the efficiency of movements, grip, and power required in the sport. Furthermore, the strong negative correlation between speed and agility with playing ability suggests that players who exhibit higher speed and better agility tend to perform better in Kabaddi. This finding is in agreement with studies conducted by Chatterjee et al. (2019) and Sharma and Sharma (2021), which demonstrated that agility plays a crucial role in dodging opponents and executing swift raids, while speed is essential for quick transitions between offensive and defensive actions. The significance of explosive power and grip strength is also supported by research from Das and Mondal (2020), who indicated that explosive movements are critical for tackling and swift directional changes, while grip strength enhances the ability to hold opponents effectively. Interestingly, the lack of a significant correlation between height and playing ability in the current study contradicts some existing literature that suggests height provides an advantage in reach and defensive skills. However, Kumar and Singh (2017) argued that in Kabaddi, the balance between agility, strength, and skill execution often outweighs the advantage of height, which could explain the non-significant relationship found in this study. These findings provide valuable insights for coaches and trainers in selecting and developing players based on key performance-related variables. Future research could further explore these relationships across different levels of play and in position-specific contexts within the sport of Kabaddi.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that anthropometrical and bio-motor variables such as weight, arm length, leg length, calf girth, speed, agility, explosive power, grip strength, and muscular endurance significantly influence Kabaddi playing ability. These variables can be effectively utilized in talent identification and training programs to enhance player performance. However, height did not show a significant correlation with playing ability, indicating that other attributes may play a more crucial role in determining success in Kabaddi. Future research should focus on further exploring these relationships at different competitive levels and among position-specific players to refine player selection and training methodologies.

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